

Awareness-raising strategies to promote a healthy lifestyle in the workplace: Impact on well-being at work and the prevention of burnout.

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Abstract

The importance of a healthy lifestyle cannot be underestimated because it is closely related to the prevention of chronic diseases. Some previous studies have shown that behaviors such as a balanced diet, regular physical activity, stress management and adequate sleep are essential to reduce the risk of chronic diseases such as cardiovascular disease, Type 2 diabetes and certain types of cancers. The objectives of this article are to propose effective strategies to sensitize individuals to the importance of adopting a healthy lifestyle in a professional environment, to analyze their impact on well-being at work and the prevention of burnout.

To achieve these objectives, a literature review was carried out to analyze previous studies on this topic. Academic databases has been consulted to identify relevant work as well as to identify trends and best practices. The methodology also includes an in-depth analysis of studies on chronic diseases related to occupational stress. Quantitative and qualitative research was examined to understand the nature of this relationship and identify the associated risk factors.

The results will provide an overview of effective outreach strategies to promote a healthy lifestyle in the workplace, such as internal communication, wellness initiatives, awareness campaigns, organizational policies conducive to a healthy lifestyle, and creating a positive work environment. We will highlight their impact on well-being at work and the prevention of burnout. Also, the results will help to better understand the relationship between professional stress and chronic diseases, by identifying the underlying risk factors and mechanisms.

In summary, this article is focusing on awareness-raising strategies to promote a healthy lifestyle in the workplace, their impact on well-being at work and the prevention of burnout, as well as on the relationship between occupational stress and chronic diseases. Finally, by implementing effective awareness-raising strategies and promoting a healthy working environment, organizations can contribute to improving the health and well-being of their employees. This can translate into increased productivity, reduced costs related to sick leave and better job satisfaction.

This study has important implications for entrepreneurs, professionally active people, or simply researchers interested in the subject. Through this article, we hope to contribute to the implementation of more effective policies and programs aimed at improving the health and workplace well-being of employees. So explore with us the importance of a healthy lifestyle, as a tool leading to professional well-being, capable of avoiding chronic diseases, workplace stress and burnout, and promoting enthusiasm for life.

Keywords : Awareness; healthy lifestyle; well-being at work; burnout; chronic diseases

Introduction

The promotion of a healthy lifestyle in the work environment has become a major concern in the current context of the increasing prevalence of chronic diseases and burnout. Individuals spend a large part of their lives at work, which makes it a favorable environment for raising awareness and encouraging healthy behaviors. This article aims to propose effective strategies to promote awareness of the importance of adopting a healthy lifestyle in a professional environment, while studying the impact of these strategies on well-being at work and the prevention of burnout.

In addition, this article will deal with chronic diseases related to occupational stress, such as cardiovascular diseases, musculoskeletal disorders, mental health problems, their relationship with an unhealthy lifestyle, and identify the physiological and psychological mechanisms that contribute to their development. By understanding how work stress can contribute to the development of these diseases, recommendations for prevention and intervention will be proposed, to improve the health and well-being of employees in a professional environment. The analysis of chronic diseases related to occupational stress highlights the need to take measures to reduce the associated risk factors.

It is also important to discuss the roles of behavior change and how to motivate individuals to take steps to improve their lifestyle. Understanding the factors that influence people's decisions and motivations is essential to designing effective and sustainable strategies to raise awareness. Behavior change is a complex process, but it can be motivated by intrinsic and extrinsic incentives. Individuals can be motivated to take steps to improve their lifestyle by understanding the benefits to their health and well-being, providing social support, offering rewards and incentives, and creating a supportive environment.

To achieve these goals, a literature review was conducted to analyze previous studies on effective workplace awareness strategies and their impact on well-being and burnout prevention. Academic databases have been used to identify relevant works and identify trends and best practices. An in-depth analysis of studies on chronic diseases associated with occupational stress was also carried out. Quantitative and qualitative research was examined to understand the nature of this relationship and identify associated risk factors.

The choice of the methodological approach, in terms of the epistemological positioning of the research and the mode of reasoning, is motivated by the need to understand in depth the awareness-raising strategies aimed at promoting a healthy lifestyle in a professional environment and their impact on well-being at work and the prevention of burnout. By adopting

an approach based on quantitative and qualitative research, we were able to explore the experiences, perceptions and motivations of individuals regarding the adoption of a healthy lifestyle at work. This allowed us to collect rich and nuanced data, using methods such as content analysis. In short, this methodological approach allowed us to obtain in-depth and significant results, leading to practical recommendations for the promotion of a healthy lifestyle in a professional environment.

1. Stress or tension:

1.1. Brief overview:

In 1934, the Canadian physician Hans Selye, a pioneer in stress studies, noticed that people who carry an infection have a series of non-specific symptoms that make them look sick, such as feeling weak, tired, and loss of appetite. According to him, the reaction of the body that makes them look sick is a nonspecific response to any request made to him. His observations led to the concept of "general adaptation syndrome" or the nonspecific response of the body to a negative state. And the term "stress response" was used to describe this initial response of the body to various attacks, borrowing the word stress from physics. Hans Selye noted that the reaction of the body can cause the disease itself, be it physical, social or psychological, and go beyond toxic factors or the social situation at the origin of this stress reaction. (Céline Ramdani, 2023: 32)

1.2. Definition :

The term "stress" has multiple meanings and describes situations as diverse as a feeling of discomfort in the morning or anxiety that leads to depression.

Stress is a natural and physiological response of the body to difficult or threatening situations. It allows the organism to adapt and increase its chances of survival. (Céline Ramdani, 2023: 32)

1.3. Stress and the immune system:

To try to understand how stress can cause diseases, we must first understand how the body works to fight diseases in general.

Constant communication between the brain and the immune system is carried out, contrary to previous beliefs, in which the immune system (which is the seventh sense) constantly informs the brain about the pathogenic or non-pathogenic nature of microorganisms present in the body. During the confrontation with an intervention (for example, a pathogen), a constant exchange takes place between the nervous and immune systems to maintain the balance of the body and leave it free from any pathological infectious organism.

The brain works in response to the immune system by causing certain behaviors. (Céline Ramdani, 2023: 33)

The study of these connections between behavior and the immune system is the subject of a relatively recent specialty: neuropsychimmunology.

1.4. Stress at work:

We talk about stress at work when a person feels an imbalance between what he is asked to do in the professional environment and the resources that he has to respond to them.

Stressful situations that take root in the long run always have a cost to the health of the individuals who suffer from them. It also has negative repercussions on the performance of companies (turnover, lost working days, loss of production quality, inhibition, ...).

1.4.1. What are the links between stress and work?

Sometimes stress situations in the company are dismissed or attributed only to the fragility or unsuitability of the position of some employees. Faced with manifestations or complaints of stress, it is nevertheless necessary to look for possible links with the professional context. (INRS, 2023: 1)

1.4.2. Occupational health:

According to the World Health Organization, health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being, and it does not consist only in the absence of illness or disability.

1.5. Dangerous situations:

Among the positions we can mention:

- Managerial stress: due to management methods, Human Resource Management and organizational changes
- Stress of deterioration of compassion (or indirect): emotional overload results from a career in constant contact with people in distress (sick, injured, homeless, victims, etc.) ... Or the worker is faced with situations that cause intense emotions
- Stress of external violence at work: any contact of an employee with the public carries a risk of violence
- Stress of internal violence at work (harassment): its object or effect is a deterioration in working conditions that is likely to violate the rights and dignity of the employee, harm his professional future and change his mental health.

1.6. The main reasons:

Among the reasons we find:

- Excessive workload: having too many tasks to complete in a limited amount of time

- Hierarchical pressure: high expectations from superiors, fear of criticism or job loss, difficult relationships with supervisors or colleagues
- Lack of control: over important aspects of one's work, lack of autonomy in decision-making or inability to influence the results
- Interpersonal relationships: conflicts with colleagues, supervisors or other people at work, communication problems and personal differences
- Job insecurity: concerns about job stability, possible layoffs or organizational changes
- Lack of social support: from colleagues or management. Feeling isolated can contribute to burnout
- Unfavorable working conditions: uncomfortable physical working environment, insufficient equipment, excessive noise or other unfavorable working conditions
- Lack of work-life balance: excessive working hours, frequent travel or unreasonable expectations of availability.

People who are more prone to burnout are people who:

- work very long hours and the workload is very heavy
- always feel that their work is not good enough
- feel inadequate or incompetent
- do not recognize their occupation
- must meet the unreasonable requirements that they impose on themselves or that are imposed on them
- Occupy a position that is not suitable for them
- do not have clear goals and objectives
- feel a high level of emotional intensity
- do not recognize the signs and symptoms of fatigue

1.7. Good stress? Bad stress?

According to popular thought, good stress allows employees to perform better, while bad stress will make them sick. However, from a scientific point of view, there is no good or bad stress, but there is an adaptation response of the body due to environmental changes.

A distinction should also be made between "acute stress" and "chronic stress", which have characteristic effects on health. Chronic stress is a response of our body to a constant stressful situation: every day in the professional framework, we have the impression that what is asked of us exceeds our capabilities, and it always has harmful effects on health, while acute stress is our body's reactions to a certain threat or problem (public speaking, change of attitude,

unexpected situation ...). When the situation is over, the stress symptoms stop soon after. (INRS, 2023: 1)

1.8. Effects of chronic stress on health:

If stress starts over time, our ability to respond deteriorates anyway, our body is exhausted and various pathological consequences appear: high blood pressure, nervousness, fatigue, depression, insomnia or sleep disorders, constant fatigue; stomach, head and back pain; muscle aches; difficulty concentrating or memorizing information; consumption of more fatty and sugary foods; loss of appetite; weight fluctuation; mood change.

The stress condition is not a disease in itself but when it is severe and persists, it can have serious effects on the physical and mental health of the workers involved.

Chronic stress alters cortisol and adrenaline levels, leading to physical conditions that are dangerous to health.

1.9. Symptoms resulting from a chronic stress condition:

These various symptoms appear within a few weeks:

- Physical symptoms: pain (colic, headache, muscle and joint pain, pain ...), Sleep disorders, appetite and digestion, feeling of shortness of breath or shortness of breath, unusual sweating...
- Emotional symptoms: increased sensitivity and nervousness, tear attacks, anxiety, excitement, sadness, feeling of uneasiness...
- Intellectual symptoms: concentration disorder leading to mistakes, forgetfulness, difficulties in taking initiatives or decisions...
- Psychosocial symptoms: increased interpersonal conflicts, absenteeism and risk of occupational burnout. decreased job satisfaction and productivity. (Koffi Serge N'Guessan, 2023)

These symptoms have implications for behaviors: resorting to soothing or exciting products (coffee, tobacco, alcohol, sleeping pills, anxiolytics, drugs, ...), Withdrawal to oneself, difficulties in cooperation, a decrease in social activities, aggressiveness... (INRS, 2023: 8)

1.10. Diseases associated with chronic stress:

If the stressful situation persists for a long time, the previous symptoms appear or worsen, causing health changes that may become irreparable.

In general, stress leads first of all to functional disorders (related to the stimulation of the work of organs) and then to organic disorders. For example, stress promotes hypertension (functional disorder) and then in the second step increases the risk of heart disease.

1.10.1. Mental disorders (mental health disorders):

Anxiety; anxiety attack; depression or depressive disorders; suicidal ideation; sleep disorders; professional burnout.

Depression or depressive disorders are more common when work Associates a high psychological demand with low margins for maneuvering (job stress), in the case of an imbalance between the efforts made and the rewards received (Siegrist model), in the case of insecurity in the working situation or in the case of prolonged working time. Suicidal ideation is generally associated with the same risk factors. Anxiety disorders are particularly associated with high psychological demand and a lack of freedom to make a decision. Sleep disorders are associated with psychological demand and internal violence. Burnout is associated with psychological demand, lack of room for maneuver and social support.

1.10.2. Diseases of the gastrointestinal tract:

Bloating, nausea, stomach ulcers, diarrhea or constipation can be mentioned.

Who did not have digestive problems the day before the job interview or before giving a public speech Stress causes a lot of inconvenience to our intestines ...

Why?: The stomach empties less quickly, transit slows down and the bacteria in the digestive tract trigger inflammation to defend themselves.

While some can tolerate this condition without any harm, others, overwhelmed by their emotions and experiencing stress for a long time can cause more serious diseases such as colopathies, irritable bowel syndromes or ulcers.

1.10.3. Cardiovascular disorders:

Under the influence of stress, biological and physiological manifestations change and can be responsible for high blood pressure, sweaty hands, accelerated heartbeat, chest pain, angina attacks (lack of oxygen in the arteries of the heart), strokes or myocardial infarction, which are some of the most representative symptoms of one-time stress. But when stress persists, it becomes one of the most harmful risk factors for the heart and arteries, just like smoking or diabetes.

People suffering from anxiety are four times more likely to have a myocardial infarction.

1.10.4. Neurological disorders:

Stress can cause many mental disorders such as depression, anxiety, schizophrenia, autism spectrum disorders, neurodegenerative diseases, especially Alzheimer's disease.

1.10.5. Hyperthyroidism of the thyroid gland:

The thyroid gland is an important hormone for the functioning of our body, as it plays a role in regulating body temperature, heart rate, nervous, digestive and reproductive systems. But it happens that this gland goes out of order under the influence of chronic stress as hypothyroidism may occur when the thyroid gland is idle or hyperthyroidism when the thyroid gland produces too many hormones in an uncontrolled manner.

Hyperthyroidism causes disruption of metabolic processes: accelerated heart rate, adjustment of intestinal transit (chronic diarrhea), aggravated sweating, shortness of breath during exercise ... But also irritability, nervousness, hand tremor and stunning weight loss in a short time.

1.10.6. Viral or microbial infections:

Physical or mental stress weakens immune defenses, causing viral or microbial infections.

We can mention chronic colds, angina, or even outbreaks of herpes and urinary and vaginal infections.

To defend the body, the immune system is the bulwark against any aggression or foreign body that it does not recognize. But if there are emotional tensions or frequent stresses, then this system goes out of order or weakens and some injuries appear.

1.10.7. Psychosomatic diseases or diseases of adaptation:

Itching, hair loss, redness, pimples, severe skin infections: eczema, urticaria, herpes and psoriasis. (MMA, 2022)

The reason Among other things, histamine. This chemical that is released during an allergic reaction is produced in very large quantities when worried, and is widely involved in inflammatory phenomena.

1.10.8. Gynecological disorders:

For women, stress can lead to disruption of the hormonal system and cause some gynecological disorders: painful periods or irregular cycles, disturbed or delayed ovulation. Prolonged labor time is also a risk factor on the correct course of pregnancy (miscarriage or premature birth).

1.10.9. Musculoskeletal disorders:

One of the most characteristic psychosomatic diseases of chronic stress or anxiety: sensation of muscle and joint pain in the upper extremities: at the level of the back, lower back or cervix; inflammation of the wrists or knees; tendonitis.

They are associated with a set of risk factors: biomechanical stresses (related to repetitive movements, physical exertion, uncomfortable situations) but also high psychological demand, reduced leeway, job stress or lack of social support. (ThéraSéréna, 2023)

1.10.10. Cancer:

Chronic stress, a carcinogenic secondary factor:

- Promotes risky and unhealthy behaviors (smoking, alcoholism, cravings for sweets and/or pretzels, overeating are all bad lifestyle habits that increase the risk of cancer.)
- Even worse: for people with cancer, stress can worsen the side effects of treatments. (Apolline Henry, 2018)
- The occurrence or growth of tumors by modifying the neuroendocrine immune system
- A possible factor of high mortality from breast cancer in women.
- Increases the mortality rate of lung cancer, stimulating the growth of cancer cells
- Weakens the immune system: the immune system protects us from infections and diseases, especially cancer. A weakened immune system affects the development of certain types of cancer.
- Changes the levels of certain hormones in the body: hormonal imbalance can also increase the risk of cancer. (Société Canadienne du Cancer, 2024)

Most cancers are associated with the interaction of environmental factors (biological, physical or chemical) and genetic factors.

In addition, recent studies show that socio-psychological factors can promote the occurrence of cancers via epigenetic mechanisms (epigenetics changes the expression of genes without modifying the DNA sequence). (Céline Ramdani, 2023: 38)

1.10.11. Metabolic syndrome:

Combines hypertension, abdominal obesity or overweight) are associated with prolonged working time, more than 55 hours a week. (And insulin resistance and metabolic disorders of blood lipids (cholesterol and triglycerides) ...

Type 2 diabetes mellitus,) is associated with functional stress of the "Karasiik model" (which associates high psychological demand with low margins for maneuverability and insecurity in the working situation.

Metabolic syndrome is a risk factor for the cardiovascular system. Employees who are prone to " job stress " are repeatedly affected by these diseases. The same applies to employees who are prone to a lack of social support, extended working hours, insecurity in the working situation or an imbalance between efforts made and rewards in return (Siegrist model).

1.10.12. Other health consequences:

Stressful work situations can increase the risk of occupational accidents. It can also cause respiratory disorders such as asthma or migraines.

2. Burnout :

2.1. Definition :

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), occupational burnout is defined as "a feeling of severe fatigue, loss of control and inability to achieve tangible results at work".

2.2. Characteristics:

It features 3 dimensions:

- Emotional burnout: feeling drained of emotional resources,
- Depersonalization or cynicism: insensitivity to the surrounding world, dehumanization of the relationship with the other (users, clients or patients become objects), negative view of others and action,
- Feeling of personal unfulfillment at work: feeling unable to properly meet the expectations of those around you, devaluing their results, feeling wasted... (INRS, 2017)

2.3. Prevention strategies:

The approach of collective prevention consists in reducing sources of stress in the company by acting directly on the organization, working conditions and social relations...

2.3.1. Strategies to prevent burnout:

- Prioritize tasks, organize processes and avoid overloading
- Set realistic goals
- Delegate tasks
- Updating skills
- Taking breaks
- Establish relationships and links with colleagues
- Not defining life at work
- Change the way of thinking and living
- Change the vision of work and the way of working (Adriana Ricketts & al, 2021)

2.3.2. How to stop these stress-related diseases:

Behavioral and cognitive therapy: stress acts on our emotions, thoughts and behavior and behavioral and cognitive therapy gives us the keys to better emotional management. It teaches us to relax quickly, helps us drive away our negative thoughts and guides us in the face of stressful situations that surround us.

- Approach medication (as anxiolytics or antidepressants) for a limited period of time;
- Change in lifestyle: improvement of diet, regular physical activity;

- Neuro-Linguistic Programming: it is a set of techniques aimed at changing our behavioral patterns;
- Mindfulness meditation exercises, psychotherapy or psychology (based on breathing and relaxation).

So, let's not give up. The solution is in US, deep down!

3. Prevention strategies for a healthy lifestyle at work:

At the international level, the governments concerned and non-governmental organizations intend to encourage and promote healthy lifestyle changes. Laws, taxes, marketing restrictions and well-designed environments encourage citizens to be physically active, eat healthy, quit smoking (or never start) and not consume products harmful to health.

Likewise, the professional environment should encourage physical activity, a healthy diet and discourage smoking by protecting non-smokers. Urban planners can facilitate the practice of walking or cycling at work.

3.1. Steps:

3.1.1. The diet system:

Restricting the content of fat, sugar and salt in processed foods is an effective way to optimize the diet, sometimes unnoticed by people.

Many countries are working with the food industry to reduce salt and sugar levels. Prices also affect behavior, and taxes on unhealthy foods (a tax on fat or sugar, for example) or support for healthy choices can lead to changes in eating habits.

Information campaigns about healthy foods and the implementation of clear food labels can help people buy more nutritionally interesting foods.

- Eat more fruits and vegetables: they help lower cholesterol levels, prevent high blood pressure and maintain a healthy weight.
- Choose foods rich in fiber: vegetables, fruits, whole grains, legumes such as lentils. This helps to lower cholesterol levels, prevent high blood pressure and maintain a healthy weight.
- Consume less salt: reduces blood pressure and reduces the risk of heart disease and stroke by almost a third.
- Choose the right fats: lean meat and lots of fish; low-fat dairy products; not all fats are the same. Saturated fats and trans fats increase cholesterol levels. Other types of fats or oils, called trans fats (olive, soy, canola, peanut oil), help prevent plaque formation on the inner lining of blood vessels.
- Consume less added sugar: to maintain a healthy weight

- Eat reasonable amounts (Fondation des Maladies du Cœur et de L'AVC du Canada, 2024)
- Drink plenty of water throughout the day.

3.1.2. Physical activity:

Getting into the habit of doing at least 150 minutes of physical activity a week is a great way to maintain a healthy weight, lower blood pressure, lower cholesterol levels, heart disease, certain types of cancer, dementia, osteoporosis, as well as manage diabetes and stress. They also usually reduce the risk of heart disease and stroke by 30%, allow healthy aging and reduce the risk of premature death by at least 19%.

The built environment can encourage physical activity. A better view of the stairs encourages people to take them instead of the elevator.

The promotion of walking or cycling, even for short distances, makes it possible to integrate physical activity into a daily routine. Awareness of the importance of physical activity for health should begin from early childhood. Professional premises can provide gyms and offices that allow employees to work standing up or bicycle chairs.

3.1.3. Quitting smoking:

All types of smoking and passive smoking increase the risk of developing cardiovascular diseases.

This is one of the most effective ways to reduce the risk of another stroke. Legislation is a powerful tool for preventing and reducing smoking. Possible measures include smoking bans, tax increases, restrictions on advertising and the use of ordinary packaging.

Information campaigns make the general public aware of the harmful effects of smoking.

3.1.4. Stress management:

People who have a high level of stress or prolonged stress have high cholesterol levels or blood pressure. They are also more likely to suffer from thickening of the arteries (atherosclerosis), which is a risk factor for stroke.

Some anti-stress tips:

- Identify sources of stress and try to get rid of them or relieve them.
- Involve friends and family and healthcare team for support.
- Find activities that promote relaxation such as listening to music, reading, walking, and meditation. (Fondation des Maladies du Cœur et de L'AVC du Canada, 2024)

3.1.5. Quality of sleep (quality sleep):

Sleep is essential for our well-being. It helps to repair and rejuvenate the body, improves concentration, productivity and regulates mood.

Modern scientific research continues to show its significant impact on our overall health. The amount of sleep needed varies by age, but in general, adults need seven to nine hours of sleep every night for optimal health. However, the quality of sleep is no less important than the quantity.

The immune, cardiovascular and respiratory systems also depend on the quality of sleep to function optimally.

3.1.6. Adequate hydration:

Water plays a crucial role in every aspect of our health. It helps regulate body temperature, lubricates joints, protects body tissues and helps get rid of waste.

The human body consists of about 60% of water, which confirms the vital importance of hydration for the proper functioning of our body.

Health benefits of hydration: improve physical performance, skin health, improve physical performance, regulate body temperature, prevent urinary tract infections. (NATURVEDA Plantes et Santé, 2023)

3.1.7. Social relationships and regular hobbies:

A study by researchers from the University of North Carolina showed that social isolation causes deterioration of health indicators: inflammation, hypertension... Conversely, building social bonds and relationships is associated with health benefits.

The practice of leisure activities is also associated with better health and a better life expectancy. Leisure practice allows physical and intellectual stimulation, and is often associated with social enrichment. (Clément Fournier, 2022)

3.1.8. Professional and personal life balance (work-life balance):

It's natural to feel passionate about your job and to have it in your heart to realize yourself through a professional career.

Work-life balance is a life concept that ensures maximum happiness for an employee, helping him to provide productive work in which he thrives. Both the employer and the employee are responsible for this.

Table 1: Factors for a balanced private/working life

Factors for a balanced private life:	Factors for a balanced working life:
- Family	- Productive work
- Friendship	- Valuation of work
- Love life and search for a partner	- Social work environment
- Hobbies and interests	- Flexible working hours and structure
- Sports and health	- Health measures, nutrition and physical exercises
- Sleep	- Special benefits (company pension plan, employee transfer card)
- Relaxation and introspection	- Encouraging outdoor activities

Source: Authors

3.1.9. Exposing to daylight:

Daylight stimulates the parts of the brain that regulate our circadian rhythm. By filling with natural light, you will sleep better at night.

In addition, the sun's ultraviolet rays are necessary for the production of vitamin D in the skin. The body uses Vitamin D to gain muscle tone, strengthen immune defenses and avoid infections ...

3.1.10. Do digital detox regularly:

To relax, it is better to find an activity away from screens especially if you spend all day in front of the computer for work.

This golden rule also applies to leisure: smartphones, tablets and laptops are best turned off a couple of hours before going to bed.

Blue light delays sleep and impairs sleep quality. There are enough alternatives to relieve the stress of the day: reading, taking a shower, listening to or playing music, doing a puzzle, drawing, knitting, doing yoga or breathing exercises, volunteering, etc. (Mensura, 2023)

Today, chronic diseases are a global public health problem.

In 2005, the World Health Organization estimated that 61% of all deaths, or 35 million, and 49% of the global burden of disease were caused by chronic diseases. By 2030, chronic diseases will be the cause of 70% of the total number of deaths and 56% of diseases worldwide. The increase is likely to be even greater in Africa and the eastern Mediterranean regions.

If we need help to adopt a healthy lifestyle, we should consult a nutritionist.

3.2. Standards:

Figure 1: Five standards of well-being at workplace

Source: Authors

- A healthy work environment: it is much more than the physical space where employees spend their days. It is a complex set that includes the atmosphere, company culture, values, relationships between colleagues, the way work is organized and managed. A healthy environment should be:
 - Physically comfortable: clean, well-lit, ergonomically conditioned space with good air quality.
 - Psychologically supportive: a company culture that encourages respect, fairness and recognition. Open and honest communication should be a priority.
- Work-life balance: it is vital for the mental health and overall well-being of employees. Joint-Stock Companies can through:
 - Offer flexible working hours, allowing employees to better manage their personal and family obligations.

- Encourage employees to take time off and disconnect from work in their free time, thereby reducing the risk of burnout.
- Recognition and appreciation: improves well-being at work: feeling appreciated and recognized for your work is a powerful motivator and satisfaction engine. Companies can:
 - Preparing formal appreciation systems, such as bonuses or promotions, based on the employee's performance and contributions.
 - Encourage informal recognition on a daily basis, as congratulations and thanks, which have a significant impact on the morale of employees.
- Professional development: the opportunity to grow and develop within the company is an essential element of well-being at work. This includes:
 - Training and continuous learning opportunities to develop new skills and knowledge.
 - Clear and accessible career paths, allowing employees to see how they can develop in the company.
- Occupational Health and safety: an essential aspect of well-being at work. Companies should:
 - Ensuring a physically safe working environment, compliance with safety standards and preventing accidents.
 - Dealing with mental health and providing support such as stress management programs, counseling services or mental health awareness initiatives.

3.3. Innovative wellness programs to enhance well-being and improve overall health:

3.3.1. Mental health programs:

Such as counseling, therapy and support groups, which provide employees with a safe and supportive environment to discuss and respond to their mental health problems.

These programs are designed to help them cope with stress, anxiety, depression and other mental health challenges that can affect their performance and overall well-being.

Some mental health programs:

- Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR): it is a program that focuses on meditation as a way to relieve stress and develop awareness of thoughts, feelings and senses. By learning to be present, participants can manage their stress and improve their well-being. MBSR has proven effective in relieving symptoms of anxiety, depression and stress.
- Employee Assistance Programs (EAP) : These are wellness programs offered by many workplaces that give them access to a mental health professional, counseling services and other resources that can help them manage their mental health. They are designed to be confidential

and are often freely available to employees. By providing access to mental health resources, they can help reduce stress and improve overall well-being.

- Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) : it is a form of speech therapy designed to help individuals change their negative thought patterns and behaviors. It is based on the idea that negative thoughts and behaviors can contribute to mental health problems such as anxiety and depression. By changing these negative patterns, individuals can improve their mental health and well-being. CBT is often used in combination with other mental health treatments, such as medication.

- Group therapy: it is a form of therapy where a group of people meet with a mental health professional to discuss their mental health challenges. It helps solve problems and provides a supportive environment for sharing and learning from others. Especially effective for those who face similar mental health challenges. (FasterCapital, 2023)

3.3.2. Physical health programs:

Such as fitness classes, yoga classes, walking groups, healthy eating workshops, health check-ups and nutritional counseling, which promote healthy habits and active lifestyles.

These programs are designed to help them maintain a healthy weight, reduce the risk of chronic diseases and improve their overall physical health.

3.3.3. Educational programs:

Such as workshops, seminars and awareness campaigns that provide information and resources on various wellness topics.

These programs are designed to help them increase their knowledge and awareness of well-being problems and allow them to make informed decisions about their health. By educating individuals about the benefits of physical activity, this aims to motivate them to engage in regular exercise and maintain a healthy lifestyle.

The impact of nutrition and health education programs:

- Improving health outcomes: participation in these programs leads to a healthy lifestyle, adopting healthy food choices and physical activity, which reduces the risk of chronic diseases such as heart disease, diabetes and obesity.

- Raising awareness: the importance of healthy eating and lifestyle. They help individuals understand the impact of their food choices on their health and the environment. For example, participants in such programs are more likely to choose Whole Foods, organic products and vegetarian diets, reducing the consumption of processed foods, chemicals and unhealthy fats.

- Improve eating skills: these programs provide individuals with the tools and knowledge to prepare healthy meals, read food labels, and make informed decisions about their food choices. For example, participants in such programs are more likely to cook at home, reducing the consumption of fast food and processed foods.

- Improve mental health: they provide individuals with the necessary tools and knowledge to manage stress, anxiety and depression. Participants in these programs are more likely to be followed in stress reduction activities such as exercise, meditation and yoga, which lead to improved mental health.

Innovative wellness programs are designed to promote healthy living and prevent chronic diseases and are evidence-based, effective and meet the needs of communities. (FasterCapital, 2023)

3.4. Creating a culture of well-being at work:

In today's fast-paced work environment, we must prioritize the well-being of employees. A culture of wellness or well-being in the workplace is very important for maintaining a healthy workforce, raising employee morale and reducing healthcare costs, but it requires commitment from employers and employees. Implementing wellness programs in the workplace can be challenging, but it is one of the most effective ways to create a culture of well-being.

Some management measures to prevent occupational stress:

- Encourage regular physical activity
- Offer healthy food
- Provide mental health resources and support to employees
- Promote work-life balance
- Presenting well-being challenges
- Sufficient physical environment;
- Ensuring health and safety
- Recognition and reward
- Healthy personal relationships
- Participation and independence
- Remote work;
- Childcare in the workplace
- Relaxation areas
- Team building activities
- Presentation on stress management

- Pension fund;
- Sabbatical leave
- Constructive criticism
- Transparent development prospects
- Continuing education

3.5. The benefits of a healthy lifestyle and beneficial effects on physical and mental health:

- Prevention of chronic diseases: such as heart disease, obesity, preventing high blood pressure, controlling blood sugar levels, lowering cholesterol levels, (often caused by poor lifestyle choices).
- Improve mental health: regular exercise, a healthy diet, good sleep and adequate hydration can boost our mood, reduce stress and anxiety and improve our overall well-being. Studies have shown that people who adopt a healthy lifestyle are less likely to develop mental health problems such as depression and anxiety.
- Increased longevity: living a healthy lifestyle can increase longevity and improve our quality of life as we age, which can lead to a longer life.
- Increase productivity and performance: regular exercise and a healthy diet can improve energy levels and mental clarity, which can help us stay focused and work better at work.
- Increase our intake of healthy foods

3.6. Influence on the motivation and productivity of employees:

Increase engagement, improve concentration, reduce absenteeism, stimulate creativity, loyalty of employees to the company.

3.7. Some numbers:

In 2017, the foundation for international benefit plans reported that 75% of companies implement health initiatives to improve the overall health and well-being of employees. Among the companies that adopted wellness programs, 66% recorded an increase in productivity and said that 67% of their employees were more satisfied.

3.8. Recommendations and suggestions:

- To encourage a healthy lifestyle and avoid the risk of developing chronic diseases due to professional stresses, it is advisable to practice regular physical activity, eat healthy food, try to control stress, get enough sleep, drink enough water, stop smoking (or not start at all) and not consume products harmful to health.

- In order to promote the well-being and improve the overall health of employees, maintain a healthy workforce, increase employee morale and reduce health care costs, it is advisable to use innovative wellness programs.
- To avoid burnout, it is advisable to develop strategies for reviewing priorities, updating skills, taking breaks, establishing relationships and bonds with colleagues, not restricting life at work, changing the way of thinking, living, seeing work and the way of working.
- It's never too late to change your lifestyle habits. Regardless of our age, it is sometimes possible, through such adaptations, to reverse the course of a chronic disease or improve its future.
- Adopting healthy lifestyle habits can contribute to improving our mental and physical well-being.

Conclusion

Chronic diseases, such as cardiovascular diseases, diabetes and mental health problems, are often caused or aggravated by stress. A healthy lifestyle, including a balanced diet, regular physical activity and stress management techniques, can reduce the risk of developing these diseases.

Finally, by implementing effective strategies to raise awareness and promote a healthy work environment, organizations can contribute to improving the health and well-being of their employees. This can translate into increased productivity, reduced costs related to sick leave, and improved job satisfaction.

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